

Annex 1 - AGENDA 1st Webinar

AGENDA for the online webinar (Zoom)

21st July 2020, 09:00-10:30 (CET)/10:00 – 11:30 (UTC +2:00/CEST)

Meeting ID: 920 6007 2995 Meeting Password: 171281

Link: <https://zoom.us/j/92060072995?pwd=d3h4SkYyUDdNZEVpK1RZQVM2WFNZZz09>

Speaker: Professor Elizabeth Wellington, PhD		
9:00 (CET)/10:00 (CEST)	General Welcome	Moderator Tânia Rosado
Talk	<i>Environmental reservoirs of antimicrobial resistance genes</i>	Speaker
~ 10:00 am (CET)	Q&A	All
	<p>Short CV of the speaker</p> <p>Professor Liz Wellington is a member of the Environment theme within the School of Life Sciences and director of Warwick Environmental Systems Interdisciplinary Centre at the University of Warwick. She holds a personal chair and, with her research group, is involved in the study of bacteria in soil and survival of pathogenic and antibiotic resistant bacteria in the environment. The focus is on understanding activity of bacterial communities, interactions with higher organisms and the survival, activity and interaction of human, animal and plant pathogens with indigenous environmental bacteria. Expert in environmental transmission routes for antimicrobial resistant bacteria and their resistance genes. Research has determined hot spots for environmental reservoirs including Waste Water Treatment Plants, run-off from land and storm drains (CSOs). Analysis of</p>	Professor Elizabeth Wellington, PhD

	<p>human gut flora for prevalence of AMR genes (ARG) in sewage provided evidence that extremely resistant <i>E.coli</i> were being disseminated. One of the current interests is to define microbial communities that metabolise organic pollutants including antibiotics and develop an understanding of how this activity impacts antibacterial resistance genes in the environment. Prof Wellington has prior experience of extensive translational research as coordinator of 5 EU projects and PI on a SysMO grant focused on studying metabolic switches involved in antibiotic production. Honorary duties include serving on grant awarding committees for MRC and NERC Science advisory Committee for Environment and Human Health, joint council initiative ESEI and UKCRC Translational Infection Research Initiative Scientific Advisory Panel (run by MRC) and contributions to NERC/BBSRC workshops. Major role as PI in Defra funded work to develop molecular methods for direct detection of <i>Mycobacterium bovis</i> in soil and faeces. A further relevant activity is the co-ordination of a metagenomics network, ComMet, sponsored by BBSRC and focused on handling large data sets and bioinformatics related to metagenome mining. She is a member of the MRC AMR Steering Group. ComMet website: www.metagenomics.uk</p>	
<p>Questions</p>		

This webinar will be recorded for internal distribution purposes, upon attending the webinar we presume your acceptance.